

A Study of Extent of Usefulness of Software to Perform Various Functions in Libraries of Academic Colleges Affiliated to Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati

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Abstract:

The use of computers in library resources management has mainly helped the library users to receive necessary information very efficiently. Computer in libraries is an important resource for library professionals striving to stay a step ahead in their field and for students, researchers, and faculty members. However, still not all the libraries of academic colleges have started using it (computers) to perform the various library operations. In the backdrop of above information, this study was carried out to study the extent of computer software use to perform various functions in the libraries. For this study, the academic colleges affiliated to Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati were selected. The primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire and using a survey method. All statistical analysis of the data was carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 18.0 software. In light of the results of this study, it is apparent that most of the librarians working in the academic colleges affiliated to Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University (SGBAU) feel that software is highly useful to perform library operations like, to search/locate books and other resources, for cataloguing and classification of books, to charge & discharge books, to register users or patrons, to calculate due date for book return, for e-communication, to access its Web based OPAC system, and for library stock management. However, most of the librarian's software is not very useful for ordering books and library materials.

Keywords: Computer software, library, resource management, academic colleges, library operations

Introduction:

Libraries are known for using Information and Communication Technology (ICT) both for automation of its routine activities as well as for providing search services to the users. Computers are increasingly used in libraries both for internal operations as well as for accessing information that is available in the library. The application of computer helps to avoid repetitive jobs and save labour and time both for users as well as the library staff. Today, computers are not only used as a data processing tool, but also for information storage, access and retrieval. The current development in science and technology has led to a new staggering condition about information created in the world. In the present ICT era, it becomes necessary for the librarians to use the computers and other devices in the day-to-day work. In this context, the librarians are expected to possess, in addition to the academic and professional qualifications, certain ICT skills, such as seamless handling of operating systems, use of various information management software packages, knowledge of databases and programming, acquaintance in webpage design, library automation software, technical skills, and managerial skills.

Application of ICT in library helps in better utilization of the available information. With the use of computers to undertake various jobs has totally

changed the conventional library operations. Currently, libraries are providing the unrestricted access of information in many ways and from many resources. Libraries have also started to provide the services of specialists who are expert in the fields of information and communication. Emerging technologies has affected the libraries in the following way: Web Based Services, Intelligent Return and Sorter System, Web OPAC, Networking of Libraries, Library Security Systems are some of them. In the present era digitalized databases are being compiled in majority of the library services, which are based on information technology as well as resources available in electronic formats. In order to know the extent of usefulness of computers to undertake various tasks inside the libraries of academic colleges a cross-sectional study was carried out.

Objective of the study: To study the extent of software usefulness in the libraries of academic colleges affiliated Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati

Scope and Limitations: For this study, the scope was limited to jurisdiction of Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati.

Methodology:

The study is carried out by using a combination of descriptive and exploratory research design, where the librarians of colleges of study

region were selected randomly. In this study, data was collected from 300 librarians working in the academic colleges affiliated to Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati. The study is delimited to the jurisdiction of Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati i.e. Colleges situated in Amravati, Akola, Washim, Buldana and Yawatmal districts will be selected. In this study, all the primary data generation was done by using standard procedures. Data was collected by using a reliable and valid structured questionnaire and by following survey method. The development of the questionnaire was done in line with the established principles. The secondary data was collected from the general publications, scientific

Data Analysis & Interpretation:

Rate the extent of usefulness of software in the library Search/locate books and other resources in library

Table 1: Extent of usefulness of software to search/locate books and other resources in college libraries

Extent of use of software	Nos.	Per
Very high	79	26.3
High	199	66.3
Low	16	5.3
No use	6	2.0
Total	300	100.0

Chi-square 315.12; df: 3, p<0.05; Table Value: 7.82

Above Table 1 presents information pertaining to Extent of usefulness of software to search/locate books and other resources by the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU. 26.3% respondents feel that software is very highly useful and according to 66.3% respondents software is

Cataloguing and classification of books:

Table 2: Extent of usefulness of software for cataloguing and classification of books

Extent of use of software	Nos.	Per
Very high	201	67.0
High	62	20.7
Low	37	12.3
No use	0	0.0
Total	300	100.0

Chi-square 308.187; df: 3, p<0.05; Table Value: 7.82

Above Table 2 presents information pertaining to Extent of usefulness of software for cataloguing and classification of books by the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU. 67.0% respondents feel that software is very highly useful and

Order for books and library materials

Table 3: Extent of usefulness of software for ordering books and library materials

Extent of use of software	Nos.	Per
Very high	31	10.3
High	69	23.0
Low	167	55.7
No use	33	11.0
Total	300	100.0

Chi-square 162.667; df: 3, p<0.05; Table Value: 7.82

journals, publications of educational institutions and associations, internet resources, research institutes and books from National and International authors.

Statistics Used:

The statistical analysis of data was done with the help of various descriptive and inferential statistical tests. The descriptive statistics, such as frequency and percentage were determined from the collected data, while the inferential statistics such as 'Chi-Square' test was used to analyze the data. The significance level was chosen to be 0.05. All statistical analysis of the data was carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 18.0 software.

highly useful to search/locate books and other resources in the college libraries. In addition to this according to 5.3% respondents, it is less useful while 2.0% respondents feel that software is of no use to search/locate books and other resources in the college libraries.

according to 20.7% respondents software is highly useful for cataloguing and classification of books in the college libraries. In addition to this according to 12.3% respondents it is less useful for cataloguing and classification of books in the college libraries.

Above Table 3 presents information pertaining to Extent of usefulness of software for ordering books and library materials by the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU. 10.3% respondents feel that software is very highly useful and according to 23.0% respondent's software is highly

useful for ordering books and library materials. In addition to this according to 55.7% respondents, it is less useful while 11.0% respondents feel that software is of no use for ordering books and library materials.

To charge & discharge books and library materials to users

Table 4: Extent of usefulness of software to charge & discharge books and library materials to users

Extent of use of software	Nos.	Per
Very high	179	59.7
High	77	25.7
Low	39	13.0
No use	5	1.7
Total	300	100.0

Chi-square 226.88; df: 3, p<0.05; Table Value: 7.82

Above Table 4 presents information pertaining to Extent of usefulness of software to charge & discharge books and library materials to users by the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU. 59.7% respondents feel that software is very highly useful and according to 25.7% respondents software

is highly useful to charge & discharge books and library materials to users. In addition to this according to 13.0% respondents it is less useful while 1.7% respondents feel that software is of no use to charge & discharge books and library materials to users

. To register users or patrons

Table 5: Extent of usefulness of software to register users or patrons

Extent of use of software	Nos.	Per
Very high	204	68.0
High	69	23.0
Low	27	9.0
No use	0	0.0
Total	300	100.0

Chi-square 328.08; df: 3, p<0.05; Table Value: 7.82

Above Table 5 presents information pertaining to Extent of usefulness of software to register users or patrons by the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU. 68.0% respondents feel that software is very highly useful and

according to 23.0% respondents software is highly useful to register users or patrons. In addition to this according to 9.0% respondents it is less useful to register users or patrons.

To calculate date due for books and library materials

Table 6: Extent of usefulness of software to calculate date due for books and library materials

Extent of use of software	Nos.	Per
Very high	179	59.7
High	82	27.3
Low	30	10.0
No use	9	3.0
Total	300	100.0

Chi-square 229.947; df: 3, p<0.05; Table Value: 7.82

Above Table 6 presents information pertaining to Extent of usefulness of software to calculate date due for books and library materials by the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU. 59.7% respondents feel that software is

very highly useful and according to 27.3% respondents software is highly useful to calculate date due for books and library materials. In addition to this according to 10.0% respondents it is less useful and according to 3.0% respondents it is of no

use to calculate date due for books and library materials

To e-mail and/or text patron's overdue and other notices

Table 7: Extent of usefulness of software to e-mail and/or text patron's overdue and other notices

Extent of use of software	Nos.	Per
Very high	227	75.7
High	58	19.3
Low	15	5.0
Total	300	100.0

Chi-square 251.18; df: 2, p<0.05; Table Value: 5.99

Above Table 7 presents information pertaining to Extent of usefulness of software to e-mail and/or text patron's overdue and other notices by the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU. 75.7% respondents feel that software is very highly

useful, according to 19.3% respondents software is highly useful to e-mail and/or text patron's overdue, and other notices. In addition to this according to 5.0% respondents, it is of no use to e-mail and/or text patron's overdue and other notices.

To access its Web based OPAC system

Table 8: Extent of usefulness of software to access its Web based OPAC system

Extent of use of software	Nos.	Per
Very high	188	62.7
High	64	21.3
Low	48	16.0
Total	300	100.0

Chi-square 117.44; df: 2, p<0.05; Table Value: 5.99

Above table 8 presents information pertaining to Extent of usefulness of software to access its Web based OPAC system by the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU. 62.7% respondent's feel that software is very highly useful

and according to 21.3%, respondent's software is highly useful to access its Web based OPAC system. In addition to this according to 16.0% respondents it is of no use to access, its Web based OPAC system.

To print barcodes

Table 9: Extent of usefulness of software to print barcodes

Extent of use of software	Nos.	Per
Very high	203	67.7
High	59	19.7
Low	38	12.7
Total	300	100.0

Chi-square 161.34; df: 2, p<0.05; Table Value: 5.99

Above Table 9 presents information pertaining to Extent of usefulness of software to print barcodes by the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU. 67.7% respondents feel that

software is very highly useful and according to 19.7% respondents software is highly useful to print barcodes. In addition to this according to 12.7% respondents it is of no use to print barcodes.

3.10 Use software for library stock management

Table 10: Extent of usefulness software for library stock management

Extent of use of software	Nos.	Per
Very high	74	24.7
High	163	54.3
Low	40	13.3
No use	23	7.7
Total	300	100.0

Chi-square 155.653; df: 3, p<0.05; Table Value: 7.82

Above table 10 presents information pertaining to Extent of usefulness of software for library stock management by the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU. 24.7% respondents feel that software is very highly useful and according to 54.3%, respondent's software is highly useful for library stock management. In addition to this according to 13.3%, respondents' software is less useful while according to 7.7% respondents it is of no use for library stock management.

Conclusions

Search/locate books and other resources in library

Because of the study results it is evident that ($p < 0.05$) most of the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU feel that software is highly useful to search/locate books and other resources in the college libraries.

Cataloguing and classification of books

On the basis of the study results it is evident that ($p < 0.05$) most of the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU feel that software is very highly useful to for cataloguing and classification of books in the college libraries.

Order for books and library materials

On the basis of the study results it is evident that ($p < 0.05$) most of the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU feel that software is less useful to for ordering books and library materials.

To charge & discharge books and library materials to users

Based on the study results it is evident that ($p < 0.05$) most of the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU feel that software is very highly useful to charge & discharge books and library materials to users.

To register users or patrons

Based on the study results it is evident that ($p < 0.05$) most of the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU feel that software is very highly useful to register users or patrons.

To calculate date due for books and library materials

On the basis of the study results it is evident that ($p < 0.05$) most of the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU feel that software is very highly useful to calculate date due for books and library materials.

To e-mail and/or text patron's overdue and other notices

On the basis of the study results it is evident that ($p < 0.05$) most of the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU feel that software is very highly useful to e-mail and/or text patron's overdue and other notices.

To access its Web based OPAC system

Based on the study results it is evident that ($p < 0.05$) most of the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU feel that software is very highly useful to access its Web based OPAC system.

Printing barcodes

Based on the study results it is evident that ($p < 0.05$) most of the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU feel that software is very highly useful to print barcodes.

Use software for library stock management

Based on the study results it is evident that ($p < 0.05$) most of the librarians of college libraries affiliated to SGBAU feel that software is highly useful for library stock management.

Recommendations

1. The college management should ensure that the library staff is well trained in use of latest IT based technologies for better information management and its utilization.
2. It is suggested that there should be regular interactive sessions in the college library to make the users aware of latest software packages for information retrieval.

Bibliography

1. Handa, S. K and Bhatt, K. (2017). Open Source Software (OSS) applications in libraries: Special Reference to Integrated Library Management and Digital Library Software, *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 8(10), pp. 321-328.
2. Hudron, K. K. and Emmanuel, B. E. (2014). The use of library software in Nigerian University Libraries and challenges, *Library Hi Tech News*, 31(3), pp. 15-20.
3. Khan, K. M and Sheikh, A. (2023). Open source software adoption for development of institutional repositories in university libraries of Islamabad, *Information Discovery and Delivery*, 51(1), pp. 47-55.
4. Mittal, A. (2017). Emerging Technologies and their Impact on the Libraries, *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 10(31), pp. 1-4.
5. Nazim, M., Munshi, S. A., & Ashar, M. (2022). Librarians self-efficacy in ICT-based library operations and services: A survey of librarians working in libraries of Aligarh Muslim University Library System. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*.
6. Ogheneghatowho, O. G and Ferdinand, O. A. (2022). User perception of the use of integrated library software is for service delivery in federal university libraries in the Niger Delta, Nigeria, *Library Philosophy & Practice*, pp. 1-20.
7. Reddy, T. R and Kumar, K. (2013). Open source software's and their impact on library

- and information centre: An overview, *International Journal of Library and Information Science*, 5(4), pp. 90-96.
8. Tihamiyu, M. A and Olatunji, S. O. (2022). Evaluation of the Adoption And Use Of Integrated Library Management Software In Selected Private University Libraries In Osun State, Nigeria, *Library Philosophy & Practice*, pp. 1-18.
 9. Winata, A. P., Fadelina, R and Basuki, S. (2021). New normal and library services in Indonesia: a case study of university libraries, *Digital Library Perspectives*, 37(1), pp. 77-84.
 10. Yang, Z., Zhou, Q., Chiu, D. K. W and Wang, Y. (2022). Exploring the factors influencing continuous usage intention of academic social network sites, *Online Information Review*, 46(7), pp. 1225-1241.
 11. Yu, P. Y., Lam, E. T. H and Chiu, D. K. W. (2022). Operation management of academic libraries in Hong Kong under COVID-19, *Library Hi Tech*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-10-2021-0342>